

Module 6	<u>Data Management Tools (DMT)</u>
Course coordinator	Stefano Cozzini (SC)
Lecturers	Federica Bazzocchi and SC
Tutors	Rodolfo Tolloi , Cecilia Zagni
Class duration	24 hours
Module Description	This module will focus on data management and curation knowledge and skills. It will provide students with an introduction to research data management and curation with practical examples and case studies. Students will understand their data management needs across the research data lifecycle, and they will be made familiar with best practices for working with FAIR-by-design data. After this course, students will be better equipped to manage data throughout their laboratory activities and to offer data stewardship support to the laboratory staff.
Main Topics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data management and curation: definition, meaning and their interplay. Data management as a combination of software, tools and best practices. Different approaches to data curation. Data and metadata concepts. - Data management Plans: Scientific data lifecycles. Data management plan structure and requirements. Useful tools for data management plan. FAIR assessment tools. - Open Data Repository: worldwide scenario, FAIR certification, solutions adopted in NFFA-DI. - Metadata: definition and their importance in data lifecycle. Collecting metadata. Electronic notebook. Ontology and vocabulary. Choosing a metadata schema. - Formats: Metadata formats. Open data formats. Hierarchical Data Format and Research Object Crate. Useful packages. - Scientific Data Management System: Architecture & Interfaces. Database system for scientific data. Relational and non-relational database systems. - Workflows: Planning workflow for scientific data curation. Workflows for open science. Workflow tools, libraries examples.
Objectives	On completion of this module students should have understood meanings and advantages of FAIR-by-design experimental data acquisition, be able to write a realistic and sustainable DMP, plan a workflow for data acquisition and use tools and scripts to realize it.